

Consequences of Urobilinogen on Chocolate Likelihood

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ABSTRACT

Objective is to check the link between chocolate delineation with urine Urobilinogen. The urobilinogen in the intestine is directly changed to brown stercobilin, which allow the feces their characteristic color. It can also be lessen the inaugurated to stercobilinogen, which can then be further oxidized to stercobilin. The normal inaugurate enterohepatic urobilinogen cycle. High amounts of bilirubin are establishing in hemolysis, which produced high urobilinogen in the gut. In liver disease (such as hepatitis), the intrahepatic urobilinogen cycle is obstruct also increasing urobilinogen levels. Urobilinogen is converted to the yellow pigmented urobilin apparent in urine. Chocolate is used in all over the world for different purposes. Chocolate is mostly eaten in foreign countries. Chocolate is most eaten due to its sweet taste and the attractive dark brown color. Chocolate is also present in the form of cocoa powder. Chocolate is mostly present in solid form. Chocolate is most favorite thing of children. Chocolate is also used in making chocolate shake and bake the chocolate cake. Chocolate is also used as a flavor in different sweet dishes. 60% males have urobilirubin and 55% females have Urobilinogen. These are also a part of people which have chocolate depiction.

Keywords: Urobilinogen; Cocoa powder; Chocolate likelihood.

Introduction

The urobilinogen in the intestine is directly changed to brown stercobilin, which allow the feces their characteristic color. It can also be lessen the inaugurated to stercobilinogen, which can then be further oxidized to stercobilin. The normal inaugurate "enterohepatic urobilinogen cycle.

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Chocolate is used in all over the world for different purposes. Chocolate is mostly eaten in foreign countries. Chocolate is most eaten due to its sweet taste and the attractive dark brown color. Chocolate is also present in the form of cocoa powder. Chocolate is mostly present in solid form. Chocolate is most favorite thing of children. Chocolate is also used in making chocolate shake and bake the chocolate cake. Chocolate is also used as a flavor in different sweet dishes.

Material and Methods

100 students take part in this research. All students belong to Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Urobilinogen in Urine

Color strips are used to test Urobilinogen in urine. Actually it is an aldehyde reaction. Strip becomes pink when test is positive. For this test optimum temperature is 23-27. Fresh sample of urine is required.

Study Objective

To check the link between chocolate delineation with urine Urobilinogen.

Results and Discussions

Total 60% males have urine urobilirubin and it are chocolate depicted. 20% males have no urobilirubin and are chocolate depicted. 20% males have urobilirubin and it don't are chocolate depicted. 0% males have no urobilirubin and don't are chocolate depicted. 55% females have urobilirubin and it are chocolate depicted. 12.25% females have no urobilirubin and are chocolate depicted. 25% females have urobilirubin and it don't are chocolate depicted. 7.5% females have no urobilirubin and don't are chocolate depicted.

Table 1. Relation of chocolate depiction with urine Urobilinogen

Gender	Chocolate Depiction		Don't have chocolate depiction	
	Urobilinogen	No Urobilinogen	Urobilinogen	No Urobilinogen
Male	60%	20%	20%	0%
Female	55%	12.5%	25%	7.5%

Conclusion

60% males have urobilirubin and 55% females have Urobilinogen. These are also a part of people which have chocolate depiction.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this study.

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